

Chapter 10. State Authorities for TVET Management¹

For all countries in SSA, we identified key governmental stakeholders who—to a greater or lesser extent—direct TVET and monitor quality (RQ19a, b). This chapter focuses selectively on the relevant government agencies in Botswana, Ghana, Kenya and Nigeria, since these countries reflect a diverse variety of TVET system structures. These countries were chosen because they have differently structured education systems and each of them continuously publishes a remarkable number of scientific publications. Since our work involves desk-based analysis, we have looked at countries for which information is available primarily on the internet. As mentioned previously, there are some states in SSA for which we could not access the official websites at any time during our data collection (e.g., the Ethiopian website was not accessible in 2018).

Research questions considered in this chapter

The research questions considered in this chapter are listed in the box below.

Research questions considered in this chapter

RQ19. Actor analysis: **Stakeholders in TVET policy** and education system decision-making.

[RQ19.a] Who are the **key players** shaping TVET politics?

[RQ19.b] Which **state authorities** are decisive for TVET and how is the (technical and vocational) education system managed?

We note that other parts of RQ19 are covered in Chapters 11 and 13.

Conclusions of this chapter

In each country studied, the key stakeholders are the governmental authorities (RQ19b). For example, the Botswana Training Authority (BOTA) is developing guidelines and strategic plans for the country's TVET system. The management of the system is divided among various government agencies with specific functions. We note that trade unions,

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guilds or indeed other associations of employees or employers appear to be of little—if any—significance.

Data from our internet search indicate that, in most SSA countries, the Ministry of Education and/or the Ministry of Labour are the main governmental authorities for the decision-making and management of the TVET system at the national level. However, other ministries are responsible for the provision and delivery of TVET programmes that relate to their specific economic sectors. For example, the TVET of health assistants or nurses is the responsibility of the Ministry of Health, the TVET of tourism education is the responsibility of the Ministry of Culture and Tourism, and so forth.

This chapter reviews the institutions involved in the planning, implementation and evaluation of TVET, and those that manage the administration of the corresponding TVET-related processes. The data collected through the internet research described below are supplemented and / or confirmed by the information obtained through our literature search. The research questions in this chapter are structured by country and arranged in alphabetical order. Readers will notice that the list is incomplete. As noted in the introduction, we have only included those countries for which we were able to find a significant amount of information on key actors. This is intended to provide the broadest possible understanding of the institutions involved in the planning, implementation and evaluation of TVET and the administration of the processes involved.

We note that research publications (focusing on TVET policy in the selected countries) are available. However, there is no evidence of the actual impact of these research findings on TVET policy or on the actions of key stakeholders, at either the national or regional level.

As with the other chapters, the subsequent sections offer additional details of the points discussed in the summary above. We note that this section covers policies that were published by mid-2019.

10.1. Authorities and policies: Botswana

In Botswana, the state TVET authority is the Ministry of Education and Skills Development ([↑no date](#)), which is responsible for general administration and management of the TVET system. There are four departments within the Ministry that are directly accountable for the different segments of the TVET system. These are:

1. the Department of Technical and Vocational Education and Training (DTVET), which is responsible for policy development of TVET and related areas;
2. the Botswana Training Authority (BOTA), which is responsible for developing standards, quality assurance, evaluations, and the accreditation of institutions, programmes and trainers;
3. the Botswana Qualification Authority (BQA), which is responsible for developing policy and criteria for work-based teaching, for TVET qualifications, and for the establishment of a national qualifications framework; and

4. the Botswana Education Hub ([↑Botswana Education Hub](#)), which aims to contribute to quality education by strengthening the capacity of existing institutions.

The current national TVET policy (NPVET) has been developed since 1997 by the MoESD in cooperation with the Ministry of Labour and Home Affairs ([↑Ministry of Labour and Home Affairs](#)), another ministry that plays an important role in Botswana's vocational training system. The MLHA participation is executed through its Human Resource Development Council ([↑Human Resource Development Council of Botswana](#)). However, training is provided through several actors, including other ministries, parastatal organisations and private institutions.

10.1.1. State TVET authority

Ministry of Education and Skills Development > Department of Technical and Vocational Education and Training

The MoESD is responsible for the general administration and management of the TVET system and the training and quality of TVET educators. The DTVET is responsible for planning, managing and implementing government policies on TVET. In 2001, it launched the Botswana Technical Education Programme (BTEP). The Department has a division for each one of the following functions it executes: policy, programme development and delivery, human resource management, departmental management and Brigades² development.

The DTVET is also responsible for planning and implementing institution-based vocational programmes. It provides institutional TVET in 35 Brigades offering 27 programmes. The TVET institution-based programmes in Botswana are:

1. TVET (full-time college-based programmes); and
2. apprenticeship skills training (theory-based blocks for apprenticeship training) — provided through the government TVET centres and the Brigades.

In 2008, the Botswana Education Hub ([↑no date](#)) was established. This is a coordinating office working to make quality education, training and research key parts of Botswana's economic diversification and social development initiatives. It contributes to quality education through

“strengthening the capacity of existing institutions, attracting new providers and attracting new ventures for better international engagement and improved standards” ([↑Government of Botswana, accessed Nov. 2018](#)).

2 Brigades were the first TVET centres in Botswana, created in 1965. According to UNEVOC (2012), Brigades *“were work crews initiated by communities in the villages, in response to the unemployment of primary school leavers who could not be admitted to secondary schools because of their poor academic performance. They provide artisan training through the combination of training with production. The goods and services produced in the production units are sold to the community. In this way, Brigades focus on community development and encourage small-scale entrepreneurs”*.

10.1.2. Key policies in Botswana

The key policies in Botswana are:

1. The Revised National Policy on Education (RNPE). First published by the Federal Government in 1994 in Government Paper No. 2, this policy sees TVET as crucial to the country's transition from a traditional agro-based economy to an industrialised one.
2. The National Policy on Vocational Education and Training (NPVET), published in 1997 by the MLHA ([†Government of Botswana, 1997](#)).
3. The TVET Act No. 22, published in 1998 by the DTVET. It established the BOTA as the statutory body to coordinate and implement TVET, and assigned MHLA the responsibility for policy formulation and strategic planning for TVET ([†Government of Botswana, 1998](#)).
4. The Botswana National Vocational Qualifications Framework (BNVQF), published in 2004 by BOTA. It covers TVET and has no links to general or higher education ([†Government of Botswana, 2005](#)).
5. The Botswana Qualifications Authority Act No. 24 (BQA Act) ([†Government of Botswana, 2013](#)).
6. The Education & Training Sector Strategic Plan (ETSSP 2015–2020), published in 2015 by the MoESD ([†Government of Botswana, 2015](#)).
7. The National Credit and Qualifications Framework (NCQF), published by the BQA ([†Government of Botswana, 2016](#)).

10.2. Authorities and policies: Ghana

The TVET system in Ghana is governed by the Ministry of Education ([†MoE](#)). Within the MoE, the state TVET authority is the Council for Technical and Vocational Education and Training ([†COTVET](#)). The Council coordinates and oversees TVET developments nationally. Other relevant departments under the MoE are the Ghana Education Service ([†Ghana Education Service](#)), which is responsible for implementing pre-tertiary education policies formulated by the MoE, and the National Board for Professional and Technician Examinations ([†NABPTEX](#)), which is responsible for evaluation, assessment and certification.

The Ministry of Employment and Labour Relations ([†MELR](#)) is the other branch of the Federal government most relevant to the TVET system. Its Directorate of Policy Planning, Budgeting, Monitoring and Evaluation leads the technical processes for the development of policies, plans, programmes and budgets of all activities of the Ministry. The National TVET Institute (NVTI) and the Integrated Community Centres for Employable Skills ([†ICES](#)) are two bodies focused on TVET provision. The former is responsible for the coordination of training centres under the Ministry's administration, and for testing and certification, while the latter carries out competency-based TVET provision in rural communities in Ghana.

In total, 19 ministries or public bodies appear to be involved in TVET. The MoE and the MELR are also the most important public providers of TVET programmes in Ghana.

Although to a lesser extent than these two Ministries, other public bodies are also responsible for TVET provision including the Ministry of Youth and Sports (MYS), the Ministry of Local Government and Rural Development (†MLGRD), and the Ministry of Health and Environment. Since 2018 the government has worked on a harmonization law to combine all TVET activities under the Ministry of Education.³

10.2.1. State TVET authority

MoE > Council for Technical and Vocational Education and Training

As mentioned, (†COTVET) coordinates and oversees TVET developments in Ghana. The main responsibility of the Council is to formulate national policies on skills development (pre-tertiary, tertiary and informally), whereas the different ministries are responsible for implementing the policies within their TVET institutions. Additionally, it has the objective of advising the federal government on all matters related to the management and improvement of the TVET system. The Council is formed of five Technical Standing Committees, which function as national bodies. These are the Industrial Training Advisory Committee, the National TVET Qualifications Committee (NTVETQC), the Training Quality Assurance Committee (TQAC), and the Skills Development Fund Committee. The fifth committee, the National Apprenticeship Committee, has been created recently and is responsible for traditional apprenticeships. Further, there are Sector Skills Bodies, across 22 branches, which make recommendations to COTVET to

“ensure that qualifications, curriculum and learning materials reflect the occupational standards” (†Ghana Skills Development Initiative, Nov. 2019).

In Ghana, a noteworthy feature is the presence of the National Council for Tertiary Education (†NCTE). The NCTE is also a prominent feature of Ghana’s TVET governance. It is responsible for recommending national standards and norms to the Minister and monitoring their implementation. These standards and norms cover staff, costs, accommodation and time utilisation. Additionally, the NCTE has significant influence over the preparation of the annual national education budget. It recommends to the Minister how block allocations of public funds should be disbursed regarding running costs and capital expenditure grants for each tertiary education institution. While the NCTE deals primarily with higher education and universities, certain institutions that broadly pertain to TVET are nevertheless located within the NCTE. This primarily concerns the 40-odd Colleges of Education in Ghana, which have migrated from the GES to the NCTE. They are considered tertiary, but not universities, and focus on the pre-service education of primary teachers.

³ Proposed legislation is available from <https://www.parliament.gh/> (cf., Education Bodies Bill †Government of Ghana, no date). As of September 2020, the law had been passed by parliament. However, the president is yet to sign the law in order for it be enacted and come into force (September 2020).

10.2.2. List of key policies in Ghana

Our research identified the following regulations and laws on TVET administration in Ghana.

1. The National Board for Professional and Technician Examinations Act No. 492 ([†NBPTEx Act](#)). Published in 1994, it established the NBPTEx to administer examination schemes for professional bodies and non-university institutions at the tertiary level ([†Government of Ghana, 1994](#)).
2. The Council for Technical and Vocational Education and Training Act No. 718 ([†COTVET Act](#); [†Government of Ghana, 2006](#)). Published in 2006, it mandated the Ghanaian government to establish a legal framework for TVET and a council (COTVET) which has “the objective of coordinating and overseeing all aspects of TVET in the country”.
3. The National Accreditation Board Act No. 744 ([†NAB Act](#)). Published in 2007, it established the National Accreditation Board, and mandates it to accredit public and private tertiary-level institutions with regard to the contents and standards of their programmes.
4. The Polytechnic Act 745 ([†Government of Ghana, 2007](#)). Published in 2007, it mandates polytechnics to provide tertiary education in the fields of manufacturing, commerce, science and technology, and to provide opportunities for skills development, applied research and the publication of research findings.
5. The Legislative Instrument LI 2195. Published by COTVET in 2012, it regulates the TVET system and ensures that it is linked to the National Technical and Vocational Education and Training Qualifications Framework (NTVETQF), which aims to improve and increase the different pathways for TVET graduates. It is administered by COTVET.
6. Education Regulation Bodies Bill, 2019, [†Government of Ghana \(no date\)](#), no yet enacted (as of September 2020).
7. Strategic Plan for TVET 2018-2022. Not publicly accessible.

10.3. Authorities and policies: Kenya

In Kenya, the Ministry of Education, Science and Technology ([†MoEST](#)) is the government body in charge of managing and developing the TVET system and its policies and programmes. It is responsible for education standards, curricula and examinations. The Ministry of Public Service, Youth and Gender Affairs, and the Ministry of Labour and Social Protection are also involved in Kenya’s TVET provision. Other line ministries also provide specialised TVET programmes. These include health, transport, agriculture, energy, and tourism (hospitality), among others.

Within Kenya’s TVET system, under the MoEST, there are several departments, authorities, boards and councils. This is something that might stand out to outsiders. The institutional framework seems very fragmented and, in some instances, functions appear to overlap across different government bodies. For example, the Ministry has a Technical

and Vocational Education and Training Authority ([†TVETA](#)) and a State Department of Vocational and Technical Training ([†VTT](#)). Moreover, the country has an Institute of Curriculum Development (KICD), a National Examination Council ([†KNEC](#)) and a National Qualifications Authority ([†KNQA](#)) and yet, there is also the TVET Curriculum Development, Assessment and Certification Council ([†TVET CDACC](#)). It is difficult to grasp how the TVET education system is managed and how these bodies communicate with one another.

10.3.1. State TVET authority

MoEST > Technical and Vocational Education and Training Authority

The Technical and Vocational Education and Training Authority ([†TVETA](#)) was established in 2013 under the Technical and Vocational Education and Training Act No. 29 ([†TVETA Act n°29, 2013](#)), and is the body in charge of coordinating and regulating TVET in Kenya. Thus, it determines national TVET objectives, promotes access to training programmes and ensures these programmes remain relevant—all within the scope of national socio-economic plans and objectives. Among its functions are the registration, licensing and accreditation of institutions, programmes, trainers and assessors, and the implementation of the TVET National Quality Assurance System. Accreditation of institutions is done in accordance with sections 18, 32 and 57 of TVET Act No. 29, 2013. Section 23 of the same Act requires that all TVET trainers are registered and licensed by the TVETA Board⁴, and that training providers are obliged to recruit only accredited trainers. Finally, TVETA is the body in charge of approving Competency-Based Education and Training (CBET) Programmes. The TVETA Competency-Based Education and Training and Assessment Standards & Guidelines ([†CBETA Standards and guidelines](#)), derived from Section 57(b) of TVET Act, state the duties and responsibilities that assessors and verifiers need to comply with in order to be accredited.

We highlight two more institutions in the Kenyan administration: the TVET Permanent Working Group (PWG), under the MoEST, and the National Industrial Training Authority ([†NITA](#)), under the MLSP.⁵ Established in 2014, the TVET Permanent Working Group

“promotes TVET as a ticket to high-valued career pathways for young people through rebranding and hands-on youth engagement” ([†Permanent Working Group on TVET in Kenya, no date](#)).

Its primary focus is to provide a platform for exchange between the different stakeholder groups involved in the TVET sector in Kenya, enabling government agencies, private sector companies, academia and development partners to collaborate and further their work in promoting TVET. This strategically positions the PWG to inform and advise the government of strategies, policy issues, best practices and the implementation of TVET

4 The first TVETA Board was appointed and inaugurated in 2014 through the Gazette Notice No. 3134.

5 We note that the composition of the TVET Permanent Working Group can be traced back to an initiative of the AHK Kenia (German Chambers of Commerce Abroad, 'Auslandhandelskammer', 'AHK').

reforms in Kenya. Secondly, NITA is a semi-autonomous government agency that operates under the Ministry of Labour and Social Protection ([†MLSP](#)). It has a tripartite National Industrial Training Board (NITB) that comprises employers, workers, government ministries, universities and other institutions. Known until 2011 as the Directorate of Industrial Training (DIT), its mandate is to promote the highest standards in the quality and efficiency of Industrial Training in Kenya, with its mission being

“to provide, facilitate, promote, regulate and coordinate integrated industrial training for a globally competitive human resource” ([†Government of Kenya, accessed April 2019:1](#)).

10.3.2. List of key policies in Kenya

Our research identified the following regulations and laws on TVET administration in Kenya.

1. The Policy Framework of Education. Published by the MoE in 2012, revised in 2019.
2. The National Industrial Training Act No. 12 ([†NITA Act](#)). Published in 2012, this act of parliament established NITA, which is designed to provide regulations for training people in industry.
3. The Kenya National Examination Council Act No. 29 ([†KNEC Act](#)). Published in 2012, this act of parliament provides for the establishment, powers and functions of the KNEC and the conduct of examinations.
4. The Technical and Vocational Education and Training Act No. 29 ([†TVETA Act n°29, 2013](#)). Published in 2013, this act established the TVETA as the central administrative unit of the TVET system in Kenya. The TVET Curriculum Development, Assessment and Certification Council (TVET CDACC) was also created in this act. This act classifies ‘accreditation’ as “the process by which the Board formally recognises and confirms by certification that an institution has met and continues to meet the standards of academic, training and competence excellence set by the Board in accordance with the provisions of this Act”.
5. The Kenya Institute of Curriculum Development Act No. 4 ([†KICD Act, 2013](#)). Published in 2013, this act established the KICD and the governing Council for the Institute.
6. The Kenya National Qualifications Framework Act No. 22 ([†KNQFA, 2014](#)). Published in 2014, this act established the Kenya National Qualifications Authority and formulated the development of the Kenya Qualifications Framework and its associated goals.
7. [†The Guidelines for Registration of Training Providers](#), published by NITA in 2016.
8. The Competency-Based Education and Training and Assessment Standards & Guidelines ([†CBETA Standards and Guidelines](#)).
9. The National Industrial Training Standards ([†NITA Standards](#)). Published by NITA.

10. The [TVET Strategic Plan 2018-2022](#). This sets out the strategic priorities of the Government as outlined in the Kenya Vision 2030, the Constitution of Kenya 2010, and other relevant regional and international policy documents. According to the TVETA Chairman,

“the development of this Strategic Plan was based on a review of the Authority’s performance and experiences since its inception, and is a culmination of an extensive consultative process among the Authority’s staff, board of directors and key stakeholders in the country” ([Government of Kenya, 2018:vii](#)).

10.4. Authorities and policies: Nigeria

The Federal Ministry of Education ([MoE](#)) is the government body in Nigeria responsible for TVET coordination at the national level and is in charge of the sector’s planning, research and development. The federal level authorities are responsible for policy, curriculum, inspections, examinations, the management of schools and federal technical colleges belonging to senior secondary education level. The federal government also bears responsibility for policy design, strategy and management of all federal-owned colleges of education, polytechnics and universities ([UNESCO-UNEVOC, 2012](#)). The government bodies described below are all units of the Ministry of Education.

10.4.1. State TVET authority

Technology and Science Education Department: National Board for Technical Education

Established in 1977 by a Decree, the National Board for Technical Education ([NBTE](#)) is the main coordinating body for TVET in Nigeria ([UNESCO-UNEVOC, 2012](#)). It is responsible for the accreditation of academic programmes in all TVET institutions in Nigeria and it publishes the Directory of Accredited Programmes. These are offered in the polytechnics and technical and vocational institutions that are under the NBTE’s regulations. The Board has an Academic Planning, Research, Statistics and ICT department, which was created as a result of a Board restructuring. The NBTE accredits proposals for qualifications submitted by awarding bodies, and monitors awarding bodies offering NSQs. NBTE effectively manages the whole system on behalf of the Government.

National Commission for Colleges of Education

In Nigeria, the Colleges of Education are managed separately from other TVET-related activities. The National Commission for Colleges of Education ([NCCE](#)) was established by Act No. 13 of 1989 and amended by Act No. 12 of 1993. The Commission’s main goal is to promote the quality of teacher education, ensuring that it contributes to national development. The NCCE is the government body responsible for making recommendations on the parts of national policy that are related to teacher education development and it also advises on the financial needs of the Colleges. It also acts as the agency for external aids directed toward improving teacher education in Nigeria. The Commission

has standardised the teacher education curriculum determining, among other things, course entry requirements and duration. It is responsible for determining the minimum requirements for the Colleges of Education, setting out the criteria for accrediting teacher education courses and the certificates awarded by the Colleges, a process which is reviewed every five years. The NCCE collates, analyses and publishes relevant information relating to teacher education in Nigeria, determining Nigerian teachers' needs and addressing them by creating master plans for the development of the 152 Colleges of Education under its administration (21 Federal Colleges, 47 State Colleges, 61 Private Colleges, 9 Polytechnics offering NCE and 14 other NCE-awarding institutions).

It is worth noting the extensive availability of information regarding Nigerian laws and regulations; we had access to policies dating back from the 1970s. Nigeria was one of the few countries where a comprehensive list of official documents was easily found and accessed. Among these were national standards for the establishment of institutions, for the approval of programmes and for certification. The Government has produced guidelines for the establishment of private TVET institutions and for the establishment and operation of the production unit in TVET colleges.

10.4.2. List of key policies in Nigeria

Our research identified the following regulations and laws on vocational training administration in Nigeria.

1. [†National Board for Technical Education Act](#). Published in 1977, this act established the National Board for Technical Education as a body to advise the Federal Government on all aspects of technical education that fall outside the scope of universities.
2. [†Federal Polytechnics Act](#). Published in 1979, this act established polytechnics in various parts of the country to provide full-time courses in technology, applied science, management and other fields. It also made provisions for the general administration of such polytechnics.
3. [†Education National Minimum Standards and Establishment of Institutions Act No. 16](#). Published in 1985, this act lists the various authorities empowered to prescribe minimum standards of education in Nigeria; and to impose penalties for any contravention of its provisions. The document contains a section on secondary and teacher education and another section on technical education. It states the purpose of TVET and teacher education, as well as the minimum standards for each of them.
4. [Federal Polytechnic Amendment Act No. 5 \(1993\)](#) by the Federal Government. The amendment provides for the post of deputy rectors for all federal polytechnics. It also sets out the tenure of office of the principal officers of the federal polytechnics.
5. [†Federal Colleges of Education Act](#). Published in 1986, this act established the Federal Colleges of Education, which are listed in the Act. Their function is, among other things, to provide full-time courses on teaching, instruction and

training in technology, applied science, commerce, arts, social sciences, humanities and management, and to carry out research on the development and adaptation of techniques. This act also makes provision for the appointment of a Provost and of the officials of each College: they carry the responsibility for the administration of education of the college students.

6. †[Educational Correspondence Colleges Accreditation Act No. 32](#). Published in 1987, this act made accreditation by the Minister of Education a precondition for the operation (or continuation in business in the case of existing institutions) of all private educational correspondence colleges wishing to conduct business in Nigeria.
7. †[Nigerian Educational Research and Development Council Act](#). Published in 1987, this act established the Nigerian Educational Research and Development Council, which was responsible for encouraging, promoting and coordinating educational research programmes in Nigeria; identifying and determining the priority of educational problems; and undertaking book, language and curriculum development, among other things.
8. †[National Commission for Colleges of Education Act](#). Published in 1989, this act established the National Commission for Colleges of Education which is responsible for advising the Federal Government on all aspects of teacher education falling outside the universities and polytechnics, among other things.
9. †[National Business and Technical Examinations Board Act](#). Published in 1993, this act established the National Business and Technical Examinations Board and gave it responsibility for the general control of the conduct of technical and business examinations hitherto conducted by the Royal Society of Arts of London City and Guilds of London and the West African Examinations Council.
10. †[National Centre for Women Development Act](#). Published in 1995, this act established the National Centre for Women Development for the general purpose of designing developmental programmes and activities for the advancement of women in Nigeria.
11. †[National Occupational Standards](#). These are standards of effective performance or competences an individual must achieve when carrying out functions in the workplace. Developed by employers and other key stakeholders and approved and published by the NBTE, NOS set out the skills, knowledge and understanding required to perform competently in the workplace. NOS also publishes measurable performance outcomes, covering the technical requirements; and the individual's ability to organise their work, make judgements, solve problems, and improve work processes and their interpersonal skills.
12. †[National Skills Qualification](#). These are work-related, competency-based qualifications. The NSQ standards are sector-specific and are set by the industry itself, reflecting the skills and knowledge that individuals need to perform a job effectively. There are NSQs available in five sectors (hospitality and tourism, power / energy / engineering, building construction, service and agro-processing), and they are regularly reviewed and updated. They are available to adults and young

people alike, as there are no minimum academic entry criteria. NSQ qualification at level 1, 2 or 3 can be taken as part of an apprenticeship. These skills are assessed at both the training centre and in the workplace. The NSQ system is maintained by

- a. the sector skills councils (whose function is to identify, define and update employment-based standards of competence);
 - b. the awarding bodies (charged with designing assessment and quality assurance systems for accreditation of the qualifications, and with approving training centres to offer NSQ);
 - c. the regulatory body (the NBTE);
 - d. assessment centres (which assess NSQ according to the awarding body criteria);
 - e. training providers (which provide training in partnership with the industry, register candidates, and assess and guide candidates towards achieving NSQs).
13. † **Nigerian Skills Qualification Framework**. Formerly known as the National Vocational Qualification Framework (NVQF), it is defined as
“a system for the development, classification and recognition of skills, knowledge and competencies acquired by individuals, irrespective of where and how the training or skill was acquired”.⁶

The objective of the Framework is to establish pathways and progression from informal to formal professional courses, indicating the comparability of different qualifications and how one can progress from one level to another. Additionally, it aspires to ensure the quality, status, relevance and provision of TVET in Nigeria. According to the NBTE, the NSQF is used to increase the influence of employers' and workers' organisations in developing competency standards for qualifications, with the goal of making the system more responsive to the needs of the labour market.

14. † **Guidelines for Establishment and Operation of Production Unit in Technical Colleges, 2006**. Published by the NBTE in 2006, this is a revised version of the policy that was first implemented 20 years ago. It was designed to make the process simpler and less time-consuming, potentially allowing more private polytechnics and monotechnics to apply for admission. A Production Unit is an outfit for producing goods or providing services by utilising all the available resources in a college. It carries the dual objective of providing practical skills training to students and generating income to augment the school's financial resources for sustaining operations and maintenance.
15. † **Standards and criteria for approval of programmes in vocational enterprise institutions and innovation enterprise institutions programmes, 2007**. Published by the NBTE in 2007, this document established the requirements for the approval of competency-based programmes offered by the then newly created VEIs

6 † **National Board for Technical Education, Nigerian Skills Qualification Framework**, available at <https://net.nbte.gov.ng/nsqf>

and IEIs. These are private institutions that provide an alternative route to higher education. The lists of approved programmes and institutional information can be seen on the NBTE website (see: † VEI and †IEI).

16. †Standards for Accreditation and Re-accreditation of Diploma Programmes in Polytechnics and Similar Post-Secondary Technical institutions in Nigeria. The third revised edition of this document was published by the NBTE in 2013, in light of global trends and new challenges in the TVET sector. Some of the changes include the introduction of the National Innovation Diploma (NID), and requirements for Entrepreneurship Education and the Nigerian Skills Qualifications Framework (NSQF).
17. †Guidelines and procedures for the establishment of private technical and technological institutions in Nigeria. Published in 2014 by the NBTE, these guidelines and procedures were established with the intention of simplifying the process of application and approval of TVET institutions.
18. †Guidelines for Establishing New Programmes in Polytechnics and Similar Tertiary Institutions in Nigeria. Published in 2013 by the NBTE and currently in its third edition, this document is “an update from previous editions which reflects current trends and changes in technical and vocational education sector” (p.ii). It incorporates the new requirements for entrepreneurship training aimed at making graduates more self-reliant in the face of the challenges of rising unemployment.
19. †Directory of accredited programmes offered in polytechnics, technical and vocational institutions in Nigeria. Currently in its 19th edition,
“the purpose of publishing this Directory is to inform academic institutions, scholarship boards, employers of labour, stakeholders in the technical education sector, parents and prospective students about the accreditation statuses of programmes that are offered by these institutions” (†anon. Executive Secretary's Office, 2017).

Hence, it contains information on certificates offered by Polytechnics, Colleges of Agriculture, Innovation Enterprise Institutions (IEI), Colleges of Health Sciences, Specialised Institutions, Technical Colleges and Vocational Enterprise Institutions (VEI).

10.5. Chapter bibliography

This bibliography can be accessed from the [↑entry for this document in our evidence library](#).

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